

Synthesis of 2'-Hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyisoflavone

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2'-Hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyisoflavone has been prepared both by partial methylation of 7,2',4'-trihydroxyisoflavone and by partial demethylation of the trimethoxy compound. Its constitution is established by ethylation and independent synthesis of the ethyl ether.

In natural products, 2'-hydroxyisoflavonoids are far more common than similarly substituted flavonoids. These were known earlier as component units in rotenoids. The synthesis of rotenoids based on this consideration has been pursued in this laboratory (Seshadri *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, **37A**, 791; 1955, **42A**, 36, 192; 1958, **47A**, 292; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 76). Munduserone (Finch and Ollis, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 176, 177), recently discovered, is a simpler member of this type. Certain isoflavone derivatives, like pterocarpin and homopteroicarpin, also have this unit and recently the synthesis of homopteroicarpin has been carried out by following this idea (Aghoramurthy *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, **30**, 218). Several 3-phenylcoumarin derivatives (wedelolactone type) that have been recently discovered have also a condensed furan ring. These are based on the 2'-hydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin system, which is very closely analogous to the corresponding isoflavone structure. Their synthesis has also been based on the initial formation of the 2'-hydroxy compounds.

In the synthesis of the complex molecules, mentioned above, there is need for the preparation of isoflavones with the 2'-hydroxyl free and the others methylated. Success has now been achieved in this work both by partial methylation of polyhydroxy-isoflavones and by partial demethylation of their full methyl ethers. As a typical example, the preparation of 7, 4'-dimethoxy-2'-hydroxyisoflavone (IV) is described in this paper.

Hydroxy-isoflavones can be partially methylated or demethylated based on the difference in reactivity of the various hydroxyl groups. Thus a hydroxyl at the 7-position is rendered more reactive by electromeric polarization arising from the carbonyl (I). This carbonyl further deactivates the hydroxyl in 5-position by chelation. Apparently hydroxyls in the side phenyl do not seem to be affected by this influence.

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| $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{(a): } R'' = H; R = R' = OH. \\ \text{(b): } R = R'' = H; R' = OH. \\ \text{(c): } R = R' = R'' = OH. \\ \text{(d): } R = R'' = OH; R' = OMe. \end{array} \right.$ | $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{(a): } R = R' = Me. \\ \text{(b): } R = Me; R' = H. \\ \text{(c): } R = H; R' = Me. \\ \text{(d): } R = R' = H. \end{array} \right.$ |
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minium chloride (4 g.) for 6 hrs. on a steam bath. The benzene was distilled and the residue decomposed with ice and HCl. The solid obtained was macerated with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%). The carbonate solution furnished on acidification the desired isoflavone which crystallised from aqueous acetone as almost colorless needles (1 g.), m. p. 284° with darkening. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 4.3. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 66.7; H, 3.7%).

7-Methoxy-2',4'-dihydroxyisoflavone.—A mixture of the above isoflavone (1.2 g.), dimethyl sulphate (0.42 c.c.), potassium carbonate (4 g.), and dry acetone (300 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hrs. on a water bath. Potassium salts were filtered, washed with dry acetone, and the combined acetone extract was evaporated. The residue was macerated with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%) to remove the unchanged trihydroxyisoflavone. 7-Methoxy-2',4'-dihydroxyisoflavone (1 g.) crystallised from ethanol as colorless needles, m. p. 212°. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.6; H, 4.2%).

7, 4'-Dimethoxy-2'-hydroxyisoflavone (IV).—The preceding isoflavone (500 mg.), dimethyl sulphate (0.16 c.c.), potassium carbonate (2 g.), and dry acetone (150 c.c.) were refluxed for 3 hrs. on a water bath. Potassium salts were filtered, washed with dry acetone, and the combined acetone extract was distilled to remove the acetone. The residue was taken in ether and the ethereal solution extracted with aqueous NaOH (2%).

The ether solution was dried over ignited sodium sulphate and then the ether distilled. Trimethoxy-isoflavone (70 mg.) crystallised from benzene as colorless prisms, m. p. 148°.

The alkali-soluble portion was acidified, the solid filtered, and after drying was extracted in a Soxhlet with ethyl acetate. 7,4'-Dimethoxy-2'-hydroxyisoflavone (280 mg.) crystallised as needles in the receiver when the extract was cooled, m. p. 183-84°. It gave no colour with ethanolic ferric chloride. It is soluble in 2% alkali. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.4; H, 4.7%). The *acetate*, prepared by refluxing the isoflavone with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate for 1 hr., crystallised from dilute acetic acid as long colorless needles, m. p. 143°. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 5.0. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 67.3; H, 4.7%).

The residue in the thimble of the Soxhlet after two crystallisations from ethanol separated as colorless needles, m. p. 212°, which was shown to be 7-methoxy-2',4'-dihydroxyisoflavone by comparison and mixed m. p.

7,4'-Dimethoxy-2'-ethoxyisoflavone (VI).—The isoflavone (IV) (0.2 g.), diethyl sulphate (0.13 c.c.), potassium carbonate (1 g.), and dry acetone (75 c.c.) were refluxed for 6 hrs. on a water bath. The product was macerated with aqueous NaOH (5%) and filtered. The insoluble 7,4'-dimethoxy-2'-ethoxyisoflavone (0.2 g.) crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (60-80°) as clusters of tiny needles, m. p. 132°. (Found: C, 69.9; H, 5.4. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 69.9; H, 5.5%). U.V. absorption in methanol showed maxima at 240 and 287 μ . A mixed m. p. with an authentic sample synthesised, as described later, showed no depression.

Partial Demethylation of 7,2',4'-Trimethoxyisoflavone

Using Aluminium Chloride-acetonitrile.—7,2',4'-Trimethoxyisoflavone (2 g.), anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.), and dry acetonitrile (50 c.c.) were refluxed for 6 hrs. on a steam bath. Acetonitrile was distilled and ice and HCl were added to decompose the

complex. The product was macerated with aqueous NaOH (2%) and filtered to remove the insoluble material which was found to be unchanged isoflavone. Alkaline extract on acidification gave 7, 4'-dimethoxy-2'-hydroxyisoflavone which crystallised as colorless needles (1.4 g.) from ethyl acetate, m.p. 183-84°. Mixed m.p. with the earlier sample of 7,4'-dimethoxy-2' hydroxyisoflavone obtained by the partial methylation of 7-methoxy-2', 4'-dihydroxyisoflavone was undepressed.

Methylation of the above isoflavone using dimethyl sulphate and acetone-potassium carbonate yielded 7,2',4'-trimethoxyisoflavone, m.p. 148°, whereas ethylation using diethyl sulphate and acetone-potassium carbonate gave 7,4'-dimethoxy-2'-ethoxyisoflavone, m.p. 132°.

Using Aluminium Chloride-nitrobenzene.—A solution of aluminium chloride (3 g.) and 7, 2', 4'-trimethoxyisoflavone (1 g.) in nitrobenzene (10 c.c.) was heated on a steam bath for 3 hrs. The mixture was decomposed with ice and HCl. The product was taken up in ether and extracted with 5% aqueous NaOH (2 × 20 c.c.). The alkaline extract was acidified and the product crystallised from a large volume of hot ethyl acetate when 7-methoxy-2',4'-dihydroxyisoflavone crystallised as needles (0.5g.), m.p. 212°. The mother liquors on further concentration gave 7, 4'-dimethoxy-2'-hydroxyisoflavone (0.2g.) which after one more crystallisation from ethyl acetate gave needles, m.p. 183-84°.

2-Ethoxy-4-methoxyphenylacetic Acid.—2-Ethoxy-4-methoxyacetophenone (34 g.), morpholine (33 c.c.) and sulphur (12 g.) were heated under reflux for 11 hrs. Excess of morpholine was removed from the chloroform solution of the product with dilute hydrochloric acid and the crude morpholide was refluxed for 11 hrs. with NaOH (105 g.) in water (800 c.c.), cooled, and filtered through a bed of hyflo-super-cel; the filtrate was acidified with HCl. The precipitated acid containing sulphur was macerated with aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate, filtered, and acidified when the product separated as a brown solid (20 g.). Crystallisation from benzene-light petroleum (60-80°) gave the acid as colorless needles, m.p. 112-13°. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 6.9. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 62.8; H, 6.7%).

2-Ethoxy-4-methoxyphenylacetamide.—A solution of the acid (5.5 g.) in chloroform (44 c.c.) containing PCl_5 (7.7 c.c.) was kept at room temperature for 2 hrs. and then warmed to 60° for 1 min. The clear solution was decanted and chloroform was removed under reduced pressure when the acid chloride was obtained as a pale brown oil. This acid chloride was gradually added in the course of 15 to 20 mins. with constant stirring to ice-cold liquor ammonia (25 c.c.). The solid separating was crystallised from hot water when the amide was obtained as colorless plates (4 g.), m.p. 131°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 7.2. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 63.1; H, 7.2%).

2-Ethoxy-4-methoxyphenylacetonitrile.—The preceding dry amide (4 g.) was mixed with P_2O_5 (8 g.) and the mixture was gently distilled under reduced pressure when the nitrile passed over as a liquid which quickly solidified (1.9 g.). It crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (60-80°) as colorless, elongated prisms, m.p. 49-50°. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 7.3. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C, 69.1; H, 6.8%).

2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl-2-ethoxy-4-methoxybenzyl Ketone.—The above nitrile (1.8 g.) and dry resorcinol (3.5 g.) were dissolved in dry ether and fused zinc chloride (1.5 g.) was added. The mixture was saturated with dry HCl gas for 4 hrs. and kept at 0° in an ice-box for 3 days. Ether layer was removed and the solid ketimine hydrochloride washed with dry ether and

then hydrolysed by heating with water (75 c.c.) on a water bath for 6 hrs. The resulting solid was crystallised from dilute ethanol when the desired ketone (0.6 g.) was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 120-21°. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 67.5; H, 6.0%).

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl-2-ethoxy-4-methoxybenzyl Ketone (V).—A solution of the above ketone (0.5 g.) in dry acetone (30 c.c.), dimethyl sulphate (0.17 c.c.) and ignited potassium carbonate (1 g.) were refluxed on a water bath for 6 hrs. The potassium salts were filtered, washed with dry acetone, and the combined acetone extract was evaporated. The residue was macerated with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%) to remove any dihydroxyketone and then crystallised from ethanol when the ketone (0.45 g.) was obtained as colorless prisms, m.p. 106°. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 6.5. $C_{18}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 68.3; H, 6.3%).

7,4'-Dimethoxy-2'-ethoxyisoflavone (VI).—A solution of the ketone (V) (0.4 g.) in dry ethyl formate (10 c.c.) was added in small portions to powdered sodium (0.4 g.) at 0°, the mixture being stirred continuously. It was stirred further for another 6 hrs. and then kept at 0° for 48 hrs. Ice-water and dilute HCl were added. The product was taken in glacial acetic acid (8 c.c.), refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., and diluted with water to obtain the ethoxyisoflavone (VI) (0.2 g.). It crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (60-80°) as colorless, small needles, m.p. 132°, undepressed by a sample described previously.